

UZBEKISTAN PARTICIPATES IN INTERNATIONAL EVALUATION PROGRAMS AS PIRLS, TIMSS, TALIS, PISA

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Annotation: *An article is about conducting international surveys, as in assessing the achievements of students, schoolchildren, teachers and even parents.*

Keywords: *prills, timss, talis, pisa*

PIRLS - how schoolchildren read and understand texts; *What is checked.* How schoolchildren know how to read and understand texts; *Who is participating?* The study involves children who graduate from elementary school.

TIMSS - how mathematics and natural sciences know in primary and high school

What is checked. The main goal of the study is to compare the quality of mathematical and natural science education in primary and secondary schools.

Who is participating? Pupils of 4th and 8th grades.

TALIS - How teachers teach; *What and whom they check.* Not schoolchildren, but teachers and directors of schools are checked. Researchers draw conclusions based on the survey - features of teaching, belief and installation of teachers, teaching methods, work satisfaction, confidence in their professional abilities, the context in which teachers and director work.

PISA - what is the level of knowledge of students in high school; Checks the mathematical, natural science and reader literacy of schoolchildren; Participates, unlike PIRLS, in this study 15-year-old students.

According to the Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to organize international research in the field of assessing the quality of education in the system of public education", the introduction of international studies PIRLS, TIMSS, PISA and TALIS in Uzbekistan Under the Inspection, the National Center for International Research on Education Quality Assessment was established.

These international assessment programs and their studies are organized by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) in cooperation with countries around the world on a regular basis.

According to the agreement signed between the State Inspectorate for Quality Control of Education and the OECD and the IEA, Uzbekistan began participating in the PISA-2022 International Student Assessment (formerly PISA-2021) and the PIRLS-2021 International Student Literacy Assessment Program.

Participation in the international program TIMSS-2023 has now begun. In this regard, in accordance with the “IEA Official Proposal for Participation in International Mathematical and Scientific Research (TIMSS) 2023 Trends”, for the first time, consent was received for the participation of Uzbekistan in the TIMSS program.

The IEA leadership expressed satisfaction with the participation of Uzbekistan in the study and made recommendations on what type of TIMSS is suitable for the educational environment in Uzbekistan. In addition, the IEA invited the first meeting of National Research Coordinators scheduled for February 2021 in Hamburg,

TIMSS (Trends in International Mathematics and Science Studies) is a 4th and 8th grade math and science assessment program that takes place every four years.

In addition to comparing the level and quality of knowledge of students in 4th and 8th grades in mathematics and science and identifying differences in the national education system, the TIMSS international assessment program includes studying the potential of teachers, factors related to students' families.

The TIMSS program began its first study in 1995 and was conducted every four years until 1999, in 1999, 2003, 2007, 2011, 2015 and 2019. The next 8th period is scheduled for 2023.

The number of countries participating in the program is also growing, as evidenced by the fact that 57 countries participated in the TIMSS survey in 2015, and this figure will increase to more than 60 countries in 2019. According to the TIMSS 2015 survey, the US, Singapore, Hong Kong, Republic of Korea, Japan, Russia and the UK have the highest performing education systems.

While PISA assesses 15-year-olds' reading, math, and science literacy, PIRLS assesses 4th graders' reading and comprehension. The TIMSS international assessment program assesses the level of mathematical and scientific literacy of students in grades 4 and 8. PIRLS and TIMSS can be recognized as complementary programs. Taking into account the PISA and TIMSS studies, the assessment of the mathematical literacy of students as one of their priorities, we can say that this is in line with the ongoing reforms in the development of mathematics in the country.

Thanks to participation in TIMSS and other international studies, Uzbekistan will have the opportunity to apply the experience of developed countries in the education system of Uzbekistan, to compare their results with the results of other countries.

In the course of the study, how well do 4th and 8th grade students in Uzbekistan perform in mathematics and science compared to their peers in other countries? Is math and science an interesting subject for 4th and 8th grade students? How does the

family support children's education in math and science? How is the process of teaching mathematics and natural sciences organized in our country today? Is the process of teaching mathematics and science in Uzbekistan unique to other countries, and if so, in what ways? How do the methods of teachers of mathematics and science in our country differ from the methods of teachers in other countries?

During the four -year research period, the global allowance allows you to control the effectiveness of the education system of our country and will serve to improve the national assessment of the Republic of Uzbekistan to improve the quality of education by introducing the approval system.

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